

Data Space Phase	Skill	Learning Outcome (LO)	Comp. Level	Target
1. Publication and Cataloguing	Metadata standards (DCAT, Dublin Core, ISO19115))	Apply ISO and DCAT metadata standards for geospatial data	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Create an INSPIRE conformant metadata and validate it using the INSPIRE Reference Validator	Advanced (A)	(T)
	Data catalog integration (API, ...)	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Standards for Data Publication (FAIR, LOD, Open Data)	Understand the FAIR principle for data management	Basic (B)	(T)
	Data Discovery and Cataloguing Tools (CKAN, DataHub, Amundsen, Apache Atlas)	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	XML	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	GeoDCAT-AP 3.0	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Data mapping from differed sources	Demonstrate the use of basic functions using FME for data conversion between BIM and GIS formats	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Georeference an IFC 2x3 model	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Georeference an IFC 4 model	Intermediate (I)	(T)
	Data modeling (JSON, GeoJSON, XML)	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	SQL	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Organizational change management	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
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2. Discovery and Search	Use of standard vocabularies	Explain basic concepts of data interoperability	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Describe concepts of location data interoperability	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Explain the basic principles and layers of European Interoperability Framework	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Discuss the 'Semantic Interoperability' layer of EIF	Basic (B)	(T)
		Explain basic concepts of Data Spaces	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Understand the implications of the technical building blocks of Data Spaces	Basic (B)	(T)
		Describe basic principles and components of INSPIRE	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Understand UML representation of data models	Basic (B)	(T)
		Analyse the implications of the implementation of the INSPIRE legally and not legally binding requirements and of the INSPIRE recommendations	Intermediate (I)	(T)
	Linked data	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-

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	Knowledge of sectorial ontologies	Describe and explain specificities of 3D geodata as compared to 2D geodata	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Define and recognise BIM and Digital Twins (DT) as technologies for representing 3D urban data and the business opportunities they provide	Basic (B)	(M)
		Identify and discuss the relevant 3D geospatial data standards	Basic (B)	(M)
		Identify and discuss examples of 3D, BIM and DT implementations and applications	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Describe and explain the principles and benefits of BIM-GIS integration	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Identify and discuss the relevant 3D geospatial data standards and their characteristics	Basic (B)	(T)
		Analyze and discuss the different integration methods and approaches	Intermediate (I)	(T)
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3. Negotiation	Data Governance Act, Data Act, Open Data Directive . . .	Describe the major data policies and initiatives in EU	Basic (B)	(M)
		Remember major data policies and initiatives in EU	Basic (B)	(T)
		List the main organizations dealing with data interoperability	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Identify major challenges related to location data interoperability	Basic (B)	(M)
		Recognise the major technological and non-technological developments related to location data interoperability	Basic (B)	(M)
		Evaluate how location data interoperability may impact the Digital Transformation strategy of your organisation	Advanced (A)	(M)
	Licensing and rights management (es. Creative Commons)	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	GDPR	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
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4. Exchange and Consumption	JSON, XML, CSV, RDF,IFC	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	APIs and data access protocols	Use OGC Web Services, including OGC APIs	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Explain how a DT can ingest OGC web services and how they can make use of API's	Basic (B)	(T)
	OGC standards	Use OGC Web Services, including OGC APIs	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Explain how a DT can ingest OGC web services and how they can make use of API's	Basic (B)	(T)

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	Formats and protocols for data exchange (e.g., ISO/IEC 11179, ISO 19115, W3C standards)	Discuss the 'Technical Interoperability' layer of EIF	Basic (B)	(T)
	Open BIM	Identify and evaluate the main challenges related to data interoperability in BIM-GIS integration	Advanced (A)	(ALL)
		Identify and describe use cases, and best practices in BIM and GIS integration across various domains & identify relevant domains for the company	Basic (B)	(M)
		Identify and describe use cases, and best practices in BIM and GIS integration across various domains	Basic (B)	(T)
	Standard data model (INSPIRE)	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Connectors	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	APIs and Data Services	Explain how a DT is fed with new geospatial data layers and what the characteristics for such layers should be	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Identify different types of platforms / products used for building and using DT	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Identify and discuss the advantages of DT platforms and the added value they (can) create for urban and environmental planning	Basic (B)	(ALL)
	Data Integration & ETL/ELT	Identify and evaluate the main challenges related to data interoperability in BIM-GIS integration	Advanced (A)	(ALL)
		Explore and integrate different data layers in a DT: using 3D data models (CityGML)	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Process and transform data for feeding the DT (BIM dataset, CS data)	Intermediate (I)	(T)
	Workflow Orchestration Tool	Explore and experiment with the functionality of a DT platform and understand and illustrate the difference(s) between a DT and GIS	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Integrate and use a BIM dataset of a building in a DT environment	Intermediate (I)	(T)
		Define scenarios and explore the impact of a new building on the urban environment	Basic (B)	(T)
	Federated Data Access	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Brokers	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
	Governance	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-
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5. Recording and Traceability	Knowledge of Database Formats and Metadata Technologies	Identify and discuss the specific data interoperability challenges for building and maintaining a DT	Basic (B)	(ALL)
		Identify and discuss in detail the standards in the BIM and 3D GIS world and analyze how they relate to each other	Intermediate (I)	(ALL)

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		Demonstrate how to handle different formats, coordinate systems, and other interoperability challenges	Intermediate (I)	(T)
	Data Lineage Tools & Frameworks	Evaluate tools and software used for data exchange and visualisation of BIM and GIS data	Advanced (A)	(ALL)
	Logging and Monitoring Systems	<i>Nessun LO mappato</i>	-	-